

POVERTY AS A SOCIO-ECONOMIC CATEGORY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10223962>

Abstract: Poverty is considered the most pressing of all social problems, focusing almost the entire gamut of sociological concepts and categories; it cannot be described without passing through the concepts of economic status and income, social inequality and stratification, distribution of national wealth and living standards of the population, culture and subculture of large social groups, lifestyle and deprivation, life needs and the consumer basket, socialization of the poor and many others.

Key words: Poverty, social problem, economic status and income, concept of poverty, multidimensional, unemployed population in social production.

Poverty is one of the major global problems that continues to remain unresolved, despite significant advances in economic development over recent decades. Poverty is one of the main obstacles to human empowerment. Currently, about a billion people around the world suffer from poverty and malnutrition. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the fight against extreme forms of poverty is named first in the list of main development goals formulated in the Millennium Declaration, adopted by 189 members of states of the United Nations at the Millennium Summit in September 2000 [4, p. 213].

There are several approaches to defining poverty. In two traditional approaches, poverty - absolute and relative - was linked exclusively to income or consumption. In the modern world, the concept of poverty has expanded: it increasingly appears to be a multifaceted phenomenon that goes far beyond a certain minimum of income and expenses. The concept of "human development" believes that it is impossible to reduce the scale of poverty by reducing its definition to only one aspect of people's lives - material well-being. Within its framework, a new approach to interpretation and a new method for measuring "multidimensional" poverty was proposed.

The first definition of poverty, which later became known as absolute poverty, was formulated at the end of the 19th century in England. It dominated both academic thinking and social policy in the first half of the twentieth century. Absolute poverty is manifested in the inability of a family to meet basic needs for food, clothing, and housing with current cash income. Currently, the

concept of absolute poverty forms the basis for the official definition of poverty in developing countries, in most countries with economies in transition, and in the United States. A person whose income is below a certain established minimum is considered absolutely poor. This minimum is called the poverty line. The concept of absolute poverty is based on the establishment of a minimum list of basic needs (the subsistence level) and the number of resources required to meet these needs [2, 288-289 p.].

The most typical factors that determine the risk of ending up in one or another group of poor include: loss of health; low level of qualifications; exclusion from the labor market; low level of per capita real income and material security; high family "load" (large families, single-parent families, etc.); individual characteristics associated with lifestyle, value orientations (those who do not want to work, who have bad habits, etc.) [5, p. 477].

The problem of poverty arises as a result of a violation of the objectively determined proportions of social reproduction:

- proportions of activity (the ratio of socially heterogeneous types of labor, the ratio of the employed and unemployed population in social production);
- proportions of the state (differentiation of the population according to the level of provision with material, spiritual and social benefits, the relationship between the elements of well-being and the phases of its reproduction);
- proportions of relationships: man - society - nature, man - social group - class - society. They are based on the key proportion between the productive and consumer forces of society, the expression of which is the ratio of working and free time.

The problem of poverty is associated with social forms of alienation of a person from a person (from society), from the prerequisites and results of work, from work itself, with a significant limitation in the consumption of basic life goods, with the formation of such conditions under which the subculture of the poor turns into a factor destabilizing the life of society [3, 241 p.].

Thus, five global factors of downward social mobility can be identified:

- political determinism - downward social mobility - the result of ongoing economic reforms, the consequences of wars, etc.;
- criminality - downward social mobility is associated with criminality, with criminal behavior (theft, extortion, violence, robbery);
- personal bad luck in life - falling to the "social bottom" is explained by illness, disability, fate, poor upbringing in the family;

- own guilt, tendency to vices - the process of downward social mobility is intensified by drunkenness, drug addiction, substance abuse, prostitution;
- social isolation - downward mobility is caused by refusal to obey social norms, homelessness, isolation from society, loss of ties with family and loved ones, lack of work, lack of faith in God [3, 389-390 p.].

When studying a social situation, it is important to analyze the following signal parameters:

- the amount and structure of family income;
- the amount and structure of family expenses;
- differentiation of income and expenses;
- dynamics of retail prices in the country as a whole, by region, by group of goods and services;
- dynamics of cash expenses, the ratio of their growth rates to the growth rates of retail prices;
- differentiation of the material and financial status of families (provision of housing, personal transport, household appliances, savings);
- population health status;
- level and differentiation of education (general and special); job security and employment);
- breakdown of social ties (family breakdown, forced migration, social deviations);
- differentiation of the population according to environmental factors;
- the magnitude and structure of the use of available free time [2, pp. 321-322].

When characterizing these parameters, one should identify symptoms of the poverty problem in the form of a deviation of a specific parameter from the established norm (standard).

An alternative way to define and measure poverty is based on its assessment through deprivation, which represents a completely different tool for measuring the real needs of the poor population, which allows not only to formulate other criteria for selecting poor families, but, if necessary, to determine the priorities of targeted social assistance.

Based on an analysis of foreign anti-poverty strategies and social protection systems, it can be concluded that there is no simple single plan for regulating poverty. However, if some countries can make significant progress in reducing the multiple dimensions of poverty, then so can other countries. However, it should be understood that each country has its own characteristics and blindly

copying the experience of social protection of developed countries is unacceptable.

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